

Document title	Kinetics of Solid-State Phase Transformations in Ternary Ti–Al–Nb Alloys below 1000°C
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Issue date	September 13, 2021
Conference Proceedings	Proc. Intermetallics 2021
ISBN	978-3-948023-17-1
Acknowledgment	This project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820647.
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Kinetics of Solid-State Phase Transformations in Ternary Ti–Al–Nb Alloys below 1000°C

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Introduction

For a further improvement of the mechanical properties of next generation TiAl-based high-temperature alloys at their application temperatures above 700 °C, it is important to better understand the evolution of microstructure and mechanical properties during application. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate the phase equilibria and kinetics of phase transformations happening in this temperature range. Especially the Ti–Al–Nb system plays an important role as it is the key system for most of the TiAl-based high-temperature alloys currently in use in aviation and automotive industries [1]. In the relevant composition range, there are two ternary intermetallic phases, the so-called O-phase (Ti_2NbAl , $oC16$, $Cmcm$) [2] and ω_0 -phase (Ti_4NbAl_3 , $hP6$, $P6_3/mmc$) [3]. Both are important for microstructure stabilization and the mechanical properties at application temperature [4,5]. They form in solid-state reactions from the intermetallic phases (βTi)₀ or Ti_3Al (α_2) [2,3] depending on microstructure, thermomechanical treatment and composition of the alloy [5]. Although there has been done a lot of research in recent years especially about the formation mechanism of the O-phase [5], there is little known about the kinetics of these transformations. Therefore, this work aims to investigate the kinetics of ω - and O-phase formation and to determine equilibrium transition temperatures, transition types, and phase equilibria involved in these transformations.

Materials and Methods

By utilizing an advanced arc melter with tiltable crucible, a series of ternary Ti–Al–Nb alloys has been produced from high-purity elements Ti (99.995 %), Al (99.999 %) and Nb (99.9 %) for subsequent heat treatments in high-purity Ar-atmosphere. For the heat treatments between 700 and 900 °C, the alloys have been encapsulated in fused silica capsules backfilled with Ti-gettered argon gas. The microstructure is characterized using light optical microscopy (LOM) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Zeiss Leo 1550 VP). Phases are characterized by powder X-ray diffraction (P-XRD, Bruker D8 Advanced A25-X1-1) and the phase composition is measured using electron probe microanalysis (EPMA, JEOL JXA-8100). Differential thermal analysis (DTA, Netzsch Pegasus 404C), calibrated with Al, Au and Ni, is used for determination of phase transition temperatures. Different heating rates (1, 2, 5, and 10 K/min) are used to study if the phase transition temperatures are heating-rate dependent. The approach of Zhu et al. [6] is employed, which is an extrapolation method to 0 K/min heating rate that was specially developed to determine the equilibrium transition temperatures of sluggish solid-solid transformations.

Fig. 1: DTA measurements with different heating rates of alloy Ti-40Al-10Nb (at.%) showing the heating rate dependence of the transition temperature (onset point marked with black arrow) for the transition $\omega_0 \rightarrow (\beta\text{Ti})_0$

Fig. 2: Equilibrium transition temperatures $\omega_0 \rightarrow (\beta\text{Ti})_0$ extrapolated to 0 K/min heating rate for different alloys using the approach of Zhu et al. [6]

Results and Discussion

From the series of produced alloys, a selection was made of those samples that contain large amounts of ω - or O-phase. Specimens of these alloys were subjected to DTA heating and cooling cycles with various constant rates.

As can be seen from Fig. 1 the transition temperature of the reversible transition $\omega_o \rightarrow (\beta\text{Ti})_o$ is heating rate dependent. A plot of the measured transition temperatures as a function of the heating rate shows that there is no simple linear relation and it is not obvious how to extrapolate to 0 K/min heating rate. A possible solution is given by Zhu et al. [6] for sluggish solid-solid reactions where the transition temperature is plotted over the third root of the heating rate. If a respective diagram (see Fig. 2) shows a linear relation, the equilibrium transformation temperature can be determined by extrapolation to 0 K/min heating rate. The fact that the transition temperature is heating rate dependent also indicates that the transformation is most likely a first-order transition, since the transformation steps [2,3] appear to need compositional changes of the phases involved, which require diffusion. This is consistent with the *in situ* high-energy XRD measurements from Stark et al. [7] who showed that the reversible transformation of $\omega_o \rightarrow (\beta\text{Ti})_o$ consists of two diffusion-controlled steps. This results also agree with the formation mechanism of the O-phase from $(\beta\text{Ti})_o$ described by Hsiung et al. [8]. They observed that the cubic lattice is distorted and chemical ordering of atoms occurs, which requires a diffusion of atoms to certain lattice sites. This observation is also corroborated by the fact that the O-phase in most cases is reported to have precipitated within a Ti_3Al or $(\beta\text{Ti})_o$ matrix [5]. In addition, literature shows that temperature plays an important role for the morphology and size of precipitates of these ternary intermetallic phases in the microstructure [5], which is an additional indication for the important role of diffusion in the formation of these phases. Another indicator pointing towards the first-order nature of the transition is the fact that formation and dissolution of the respective phases are not observed at the same temperature in DTA. In case of second-order type reactions as for example order/disorder transformations in the Ti–Al–Nb system, the transition is observed at the same temperature during heating and cooling.

The present work is the first systematic study of the kinetics of phase transformations regarding the low-temperature ω - and O-phases of the Ti–Al–Nb system. Both phases play an important role for the mechanical behaviour of TiAl-based alloys. The knowledge about the kinetics of their solid-state phase transformations and the equilibrium transition temperatures together with results from complementing studies on phase equilibria are an essential input for the development of an improved CALPHAD database that aims in designing next-generation TiAl-based alloys to meet the ecological demands of future applications regarding reduced greenhouse gas and noise emissions [9].

This work is part of the ADVANCE project, which has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 820647.

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